

OPTIMIZATION OF METHODS OF DIAGNOSTICS AND TREATMENT OF RETINAL DETACHMENT IN PREGNANCY IN PATIENTS WITH HIGH MYOPIA

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1. Relevance

Retinal detachment (RD) is a serious complication that can lead to vision loss, especially in patients with high myopia. Pregnancy is a special period when significant changes in the body are observed, including changes in the eyes. The relevance of the topic is due to the need to develop optimized approaches to the diagnosis and treatment of RD in this group of patients in order to prevent vision loss and improve outcomes.

2. Purpose of the study

The aim of the study is to develop and implement optimized methods for diagnosis, treatment and prevention of retinal detachment in women with high myopia during pregnancy.

3. Research objectives

To study the clinical features of retinal detachment in pregnant women with high myopia.

To evaluate the effectiveness of modern diagnostic methods, such as optical coherence tomography (OCT) and ultrasound biomicroscopy, for early detection of OS.

To study the influence of pregnancy hormones on the state of the retina and the risk of developing OS.

To develop recommendations on tactics for managing pregnant women with high myopia to prevent OS.

To evaluate the results of different treatment methods for OS in pregnant women, including surgical and conservative approaches.

4. The novelty of this study is as follows:

1. Analysis of clinical features: The study identifies specific clinical manifestations of retinal detachment in pregnant women with high myopia, which will provide a better understanding of the pathogenesis and risks associated with this group of patients.

2. Impact of hormonal changes: Conducting an analysis of the impact of hormonal changes during pregnancy on the condition of the retina and the risk of developing retinal detachment, which is an under-researched aspect. This will allow identifying additional risk factors and adapting monitoring approaches.

3. Modern diagnostic methods: Implementation and evaluation of the effectiveness of modern imaging methods, such as optical coherence tomography (OCT) and ultrasound biomicroscopy, for early detection of retinal detachment, which may lead to reduced complications and improved outcomes.

4. Individualized management protocols: Development of recommendations for individualized management protocols for pregnant women with high myopia, including monitoring and preventive measures, which will improve the quality of medical care and reduce risks.

5. Comparative analysis of treatment methods: Evaluation and comparison of different methods of treating retinal detachment (surgical and conservative approaches) in pregnant women, which will help to identify the most effective strategies with minimal risks for mother and child.

Materials: women diagnosed with high myopia who sought ophthalmological care during pregnancy.

Methods:

Clinical diagnostic methods (OCT, ultrasound).

Analysis of hormonal changes in the body of a pregnant woman and their impact on the condition of the retina.

Evaluation of the effectiveness of various treatment methods, including surgical interventions and conservative therapy.

Monitoring patients dynamically before and after childbirth.

Conclusion: Determination of the clinical features of retinal detachment in pregnant women with high myopia.

Development of recommendations for early diagnosis and prevention of OS in this group of patients.

To evaluate the effectiveness of different treatment methods and their impact on postpartum visual outcomes.

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